

Human Health and the Environment

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Abstract:

Human health and well-being is affected appreciably by the environment around us. Life in mind peaceful calm and quite environment encourages health and well-being while life in unhealthy and stressful environment causes ill health, morbidity and a general shortening of one's life span. An unhealthy and severe environment tones our mental abilities, strains our physical capabilities directly or indirectly, induces anxieties and diseases of various kinds since times immemorial there has been a tug of war between humans and the microbes conditioned by generations of contact, exposures to immune system and human behaviour. As scientific knowledge developed better and more sophisticated increases were adapted to control the diseases. Many infectious diseases were gradually brought under control. However, micorbial organisms appear to be better-equipped to invade new places, take on to new hosts or ecological niches, change their virulence or means of transmission and develop resistance to drugs. An organism capable of replicating itself a million times within a day has an evolutionary advantage over its host, with change and surprise on its side. Therefore, no matter how much sophisticated disease control measures become, there is always the possibility of another outbreak of an epidemic at anytime and anywhere in the world. Today enormous mobility and speed has been added to this battle while infectious diseases has troubled humanity since times immemorial and have caused health problems and deaths on unprecedented scales, the advancing frontiers of science and technology have added a new threat to the human health. This threat comes from the variety of chemicals and radioactive material which we manufacture, use or discard. During their manufacture, storage and transportation some of the toxic material may escape and contaminate the environment. Twentieth century has witness numerous incidences of accidental or deliberate discharge of toxic chemicals which have caused adverse health effects and death son large scales.

Keywords: Water borne diseases, TB, Typhoid, Cholera, Health effects.

Introduction:

The environment can affect our life drastically by bringing about changes in conditions of life around us. An unhealthy and degraded environment may reduce productivity of agriculture, animal husbandry, and fisheries etc. causing shortages of all types. Poverty and the consequent malnutrition which is rampart in many of the African, South American and Asian countries of the world is a blue print for ill health, morbidity and outbreak of infectious diseases. Malnutrition in particular, predisposes people to a variety of deficiency and infectious diseases which could be avoided otherwise can a healthy diet. A degraded environment may bring about adverse qualitative or quantitative changes in many of the resources we use which in turn may affect human health. The pollution of the stratosphere. Ex. Today threatens to destroy the protective ozone shield. Damage to the stratosphere. Ozone layer shall result in highest amounts of solar ultraviolet radiations to reach down to earth's surface causing increased incidences of cataract of eyes, skin diseases and cancers etc. major human health problems associated with a degraded environment may be of the following types:

- A. The threat of infectious diseases
- B. The threat of exposure to toxic chemicals, radioactive materials, heavy metals and toxic trace elements.

C. Hidden health effects of contaminated environment on human lives

- A. **The threat of infectious:**A degraded and unhealthy environment may promote the growth of other life forms (insects and pests) that may become a potential threat to human health and well-being. Organic wastes, sewage effluents, excreta, exudates and faecal matter support a rich population of microbes. Numerous bacteria, algae fungi, protozons helminthes, annelids, larval stages of various insects, pests etc thrive on organic matter. Some of these are responsible for causing dangerous diseases of man, animals and plants waterborne diseases are caused by pathogenic microorganisms which are directly transmitted when contaminated drinking water is consumed. According to the world health organization, diarrheal diseases account for an estimated 4.1% of the total global burden of disease and is responsible for the deaths of 1.8 million people every year. It was estimated that 88% of that burden is attributable to unsafe. Water supply, sanitation and hygiene and is mostly concentrated in children in developing countries. Chance contamination of water supplies, food and other edible material with sewage effluents and organic wastes is often responsible for the outbreak of a number of diseases. Typhoid caused by salmonella

typhii and cholera caused by vibrio cholera for example mainly spread through contaminated waters. Air borne diseases are diseases which are transmitted through air. Acute respiratory infections kill more than 4 million people each year and are the leading cause of death among children under age 5. This range of infections, which includes pneumonia in its most serious form, accounts for more than 8 percent of the global burden of diseases. Overcrowding and unsanitary household conditions favour the transmission of the disease, which is spread by droplets from a cough or a sneeze or unwashed hands. Although cause and effect relationship between indoor air pollution and acute respiratory infections is difficult to prove in part because people who use biomass fuels tend to be poor and exposed to multiple risks such as overcrowding, tobacco smoke, and malnutrition.

Aim and Objective:

- 1) To find out infectious diseases.
- 2) To find out problems of malnutrition.
- 3) To study the dietary pattern.

Research Methodology:

- 1) The present study was undertaken in Akhuj, Tal. Malshiras.
- 2) Keeping the objectives of the study in view, structured interview schedule was prepared. Second part of the interview schedule consists of the questions framed for seeking the information about health problems.
- 3) Clinical Assessment: A variety of clinical features have been described (Jelliffe, Jelliffe, 1990) other micronutrient deficiency status (Malnutrition, Typhoid, Tuberculosis)

Conclusions:

The rapidly changing global trends in the area of food consumption patterns, lifestyles and environment have a tremendous impact on the nutrition and health impact on the nutrition and health profiles of the communities. Typhoid is an infectious disease with an acute fever of short duration and occurs only in humans. Salmonella typhi causes typhoid, salmonella schottmulleri causes paratyphoid. Faces of infection, drinking water or milk and food contaminated by intestinal contents of the patients or carries or by flies, which often transmit the disease. Tuberculosis is an infectious disease caused by the bacillus mycobacterium tuberculosis. It affects the lungs most often, but may also be localised in other organs such as the lymph nodes or kidneys or it may be generalised climate changes is the single biggest health threat facing humanity. The impacts are already harming health through air pollution, diseases, extreme weather events, forced displacement, food insecurity and pressures on

mental health. Every ear, environmental factors take the lives of around 13 million people.

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